

Design and Development of a Hybrid Source Vegetable Crop Solar Dryer Integrated with Thermal Energy Storage: No-Load Experimental Validation

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Abstract: In regions with high humidity and abundant solar radiation, developing efficient and sustainable drying technologies for agricultural products is essential. This paper presents the design, construction, and no-load performance evaluation of a solar dryer for high humid climate of Nigeria. The hybrid dryer is controlled by an Arduino microprocessor that automates the system using hydrothermal sensors to measure temperatures and relative humidity of the ambient air, solar collector, drying racks, and drying chamber. The energy generated by the solar and electric heat sources was measured to assess the system's capability to handle moisture-laden food products. The heating of the drying chamber by the solar collector caused the chamber temperature to rise from 35.9°C to 58.1°C. The maximum recorded solar collector temperature was 57.5°C, with an average ambient temperature of 39.3°C during the experiment. Solar radiation intensity ranged from 292.8 to 1305.2 W/m², and solar collector efficiency ranged between 40.1% and 88.3%. When the solar collector was isolated, the heating element raised the drying chamber temperature from 28.4°C at 8:35 am to 69.2°C at 10:55 am. The system's thermal energy generation efficiency varied between 50.5% and 75.5%. A regression model of thermal efficiency against running time showed an R² value of 0.9816. The system's performance was attributed to the contributions of the solar collector and heating element, with negligible thermal deficits. Experimental validation demonstrates the hybrid dryer's potential to enhance food drying rates during inclement weather, offering valuable insights into improving food preservation and reducing post-harvest losses in tropical, high-humidity regions.

Keywords: Solar dryer, crop rewetting, humid climate, postharvest losses, thermal energy

Introduction

Agriculture is the backbone of Nigeria's economy, employing millions of people and contributing significantly to the nation's gross domestic product (GDP). However, one of the most significant challenges faced by Nigerian farmers is post-harvest losses, primarily caused by inadequate and inefficient crop drying methods. Farmers have relied on fossil fuels, such as wood, charcoal, and diesel, to dry their crops. But the cost of fuel for energy to power dryers is rising tremendously in Nigeria coupled with increasing environmental concerns. Hence, relying mainly on the use of fossil fuel for the drying of farm produce is not only capital intensive but also contributes to environmental degradation as a result of its associated harmful emissions (Okoronkwo *et al.*, 2018; Igbokwe *et al.*, 2016; Ononogbo *et al.*, 2020). The upward trend in fuel prices in Nigeria has had significant negative impacts on preserving harvested farm produce such as drying, thus resulting in high market prices of processed food products. Sadly, farmers who cannot afford the purchase of the costly fuel to dry their crops are either forced to practice subsistence farming or to dump farming for other available businesses for survival, which is a huge threat to food security (Ononogbo *et al.*, 2022a; Ononogbo *et al.*, 2022b).

In the southern part of Nigeria, and many other tropical regions of Africa with high humidity levels, the post-harvest losses of agricultural products, particularly vegetables, remain a significant challenge. Traditional drying methods such as open sun drying are often inadequate due to erratic weather conditions and the risk of contamination by dust and microbial infection or attacks by insects and rodents (Ononogbo *et al.*, 2021; Ononogbo *et al.*, 2022). Solar drying represents a sustainable alternative, harnessing abundant solar energy resources to reduce post-harvest losses and improve food security. However conventional solar dryers have long suffered from inefficiencies related to weather dependency, limited operation time, temperature fluctuations, and moisture content control (Tyagi, 2018; Sambo and Ogunjuyigbe, 2018; Arnulfo, 2016). However, through the integration of thermal storage devices and exhaust air recirculation with dehumidification agents, the efficiency of solar dryers has been significantly improved. These innovations have extended operation times, maintained temperature control, reduced drying time, and enhanced the quality of the dried products. As solar drying technology continues to evolve, these advancements hold great promise for

addressing post-harvest losses and promoting sustainable agriculture practices in Nigeria.

The integration of thermal energy storage (TES) is a key feature of the system, aiming to enhance drying efficiency and extend the drying period beyond daylight hours. The utilization of TES allows for continuous drying, overcoming the limitations of conventional solar dryers. Solar drying has gained considerable attention as an eco-friendly and cost-effective method for preserving agricultural products. It involves the conversion of solar radiation into thermal energy to facilitate the removal of moisture from crops. Various types of solar dryers have been developed, including direct, indirect, and mixed-mode dryers, each with its advantages and disadvantages (Jain *et al.*, 2020). Thermal energy storage (TES) systems using phase change materials (PCMs) have been integrated into solar drying technologies to store excess thermal energy during the day for use during the night or on cloudy days (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2019). This integration ensures continuous drying, which is crucial for preserving the quality of agricultural products. PCMs have high latent heat storage capacity and can release heat energy during the solid-liquid phase transition, ensuring continuous drying during nighttime or cloudy periods (Fang *et al.*, 2021). Nigeria's climate

is characterized by high temperatures and humidity, especially in the southern and coastal regions. These conditions challenge traditional drying methods, making solar drying with TES an attractive solution (Adedeji *et al.*, 2018). The focus of this paper is to design and empirically evaluate the performance of the system under no-load conditions to ascertain its thermal capability in the high-humidity climate of Nigeria. This, however, will expedite enhancement in the design prospects of hybrid solar dryers for coastal regions in Nigeria (Nwakuba, *et al.*, 2020).

Materials and Methods

Dryer parts and mode of operation

The hybrid solar dryer consists of a solar collector, air circulation system, thermal energy storage system, drying chamber, and monitoring and control system. The materials used for the fabrication of the dryer were selected based on availability, cost, functionality, and reliability. A high-efficiency corrugated aluminum sheet absorber plate was used to absorb and convert solar radiation into thermal energy, whereas Perspex glass was used as the glazing material. A paraffin wax PCM as TES material was integrated into the dryer directly under the

absorber plate within the solar collector. The drying chamber was designed to accommodate vegetables, ensuring proper airflow and temperature control. Forced convection is used to circulate air through the chamber by the use of DC fans (of specification: 12V 0.7A; D14BH-12L). Other materials used for the fabrication of the dryer were angle iron, mild steel plates, wood, and perforated stainless-steel trays, which were all locally sourced. Fiberglass was used as thermal insulating material to minimize heat losses in the drying chamber walls. Another important part is the exhaust moist air recirculating unit which functions by providing the means of recovering and reusing the waste heat of the warm exhaust air instead of discarding it into the environment with its heat unrecovered. The warm moist air is made to pass across a substance (silica gel) that dehumidifies it. It is then channeled to the

heating element where it is heated and routed back to the drying chamber. The deep cycle battery (Tall Tubular) of specification: 12 V/230 Ah; PE-2300, charged by a solar panel of 400W supplies electricity to the heating element. The fans placed at the inlet, chimney, and heating element compartment are also powered by the battery. Balance beam weight sensors positioned at the two drying trays measure the weight of the sample product periodically. Temperature and humidity sensors fixed outside the dryer, inside the solar collector compartment, at the drying trays, and in the chimney, measure the temperatures at these points. The control panel helps to regulate the activities of the fans, weight sensor, temperature, and humidity sensors.

Figure 1 shows the dryer's isometric diagram, while Figure 2 depicts the exploded view of the hybrid dryer.

Figure 1a Isometric diagram of the hybrid dryer

The solar dryer is different from conventional ones in that it incorporates three important features (TES, a recirculatory unit with a warm moist air dehumidifier, and a heating system) in one dryer.

Figure 1b Exploded view of the hybrid solar dryer

Dryer design

A pilot-scale hybrid solar dryer of 5kg capacity was designed and fabricated for vegetable crop drying. Factors considered were the total amount of crop to be dried, the quantity of water to be removed from the crop, the quantity of heat required to remove water from the crop, and the intensity of average solar irradiance. The location selected for fabrication, installation and experimentation of the dryer was Obinze, (a few kilometers away from the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo), which lies on a latitude of 5° 24'59.99''N and latitude of 6° 57'59.99''E. The dryer's dimensions were obtained by calculating the quantity of heat needed to remove water from

the selected farm produce to the final moisture content.

Amount of moisture removed

The mass of water, M_w (kg) to be removed from the produce during the process of drying is obtained using Eqn. (1):

$$M_w = m_w - M_d \quad (1)$$

where m_w is the mass of wet red pepper, M_d is the mass of dried paper, and is calculated using Eqn. (2) (Ajala *et al.*, 2015; Ononogbo *et al.*, 2020):

$$M_d = \frac{m_w(100 - M_o)}{100 - M_f} \quad (2)$$

where the M_o is the percentage initial moisture content of freshly harvested pepper

before drying, and M_f is the percentage final moisture content after drying.

Quantity of heat for moisture removal

The quantity of heat required for the removal of water from the pepper is given by (Karlekar and Desmond, 1982; Ajala *et al.* 2015):

$$Q_w = m_w \times c_p(T_g - T_a) + M_w L \quad (3)$$

where L is the latent heat of vaporization of water (2256 kJ/kg) (Liley, 1997), T_g is the temperature of the drying pepper (°C), T_a is the ambient air temperature (°C), m_w is the total mass of wet pepper per batch (kg). From the ASHRAE Guide and Data Books for thermal properties of foods, the specific heat of pepper above freezing point, c_p is 3.81 kJ kg⁻¹°C⁻¹.

Quantity of heat stored by TES media

The quantity of heat stored by TES material, Q_{TES} (kJ) is obtained using Eqn. (4) (Sreekumar, 2007; Komolafe and Waheed, 2018):

$$Q_{hs} = M_{hs} \times c_{hs} \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where M_{hs} is the mass of TES media (kg), c_{hs} is the specific heat of TES material (kJ/kg/K). In contrast, increment, ΔT is the difference in the operational temperature level of the TES material.

Collector angle of inclination

The collector inclination angle, β (°) to the horizontal for the achievement of maximum solar energy is given as (Gbaha, 2007; Komolafe1 and Waheed, 2018):

$$(\phi - 10^0) \leq \beta \leq (\phi + 10^0) \quad (5)$$

Whereas ϕ , the latitude of the location where the collector was installed is 5.4117°N.

The size of the solar collector

The area of the solar collector, A_c (m²) calculated using Eqn. (6) (Khaing *et al.*, 2019):

$$A_c = \frac{Q}{I_T \eta_c t_d} \quad (6)$$

where Q (kJ) is the total heat requirement (drying load), I_T is the total solar insolation (W/m²), η_c is the collector efficiency, and t_d is the drying time (hr).

Determination of solar collector useful energy gained

The useful heat energy gained by the solar collector, Q_u (W) is evaluated using Eqn. (7) (Gatea, 2010; Waheed, 2018):

$$Q_u = A_c [(\alpha \tau I - U_L(T_c - T_a))] \quad (7)$$

where α is the solar absorptance, τ is the transmittance of the top glazing, and I is the incident insolation (W/m²), U_L (W/m²K) is the overall heat transfer coefficient of the solar collector, T_c (K) is the temperature of the absorber plate, and T_a (K) is the temperature of the ambient air.

Determination of the heat gained by air

The heat energy gained by air, Q_a (W) is calculated using the relation (Bolaji, 2011; Komolafe and Waheed, 2018):

$$Q_a = \dot{m}_a c_a (T_c - T_a) \quad (8)$$

where \dot{m}_a is the mass flow rate of air (kg/s), c_a is the specific heat capacity of air (J/kgK).

Heat removal factor of the collector

The heat removal factor of the solar collector (F_{rc}) is calculated using (Bolaji, 2011):

$$F_{rc} = \frac{Q_a}{Q_u} = \frac{\dot{m}_a c_a (T_c - T_a)}{A_c [\alpha \tau I_T - U_L (T_c - T_a)]} \quad (9)$$

Sizing of the drying chamber

The drying chamber's width, w_{dc} (m) is usually the same as that of the solar collector. The area of the drying chamber, A_{dc} (m²) is expressed as seen in Eqn. (10):

$$A_{dc} = L_{dc} \times w_{dc} \quad (10)$$

where L_{dc} (m) is the length of the drying chamber.

Performance evaluation of the dryer

The test rig of the hybrid solar dryer was fabricated and installed at a workshop at Obinze, which is very close to the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria, and after that was subjected to performance evaluation. A

series of experiments were conducted using the integrated solar dryer. Variables such as drying temperature, relative humidity, and time were monitored. Two distinct experiments were conducted to study the temperature profile of the drying chamber under no load condition. One involved the heating of the drying chamber using the solar collector when the heating element was switched off, while the other involved the heating of the drying chamber with the heating element when the solar collector was isolated.

Efficiency of the solar collector

The solar collector efficiency (η_c) is calculated using (Sevik, 2014; Komolafe and Waheed, 2018; Nwakuba *et al.*, 2020):

$$\eta_c = \frac{\dot{m}_a c_a (T_c - T_a)}{I_T A_c} \quad (11)$$

where $I_T A_c$ is the available solar energy to the collector.

Experimental procedure

No load test conditions of the dryer

The test rig of the hybrid solar dryer was installed in an open space around Engr. Emuka's workshop in Obinze, which has a large sunny space. The dryer was subjected to no load test conditions to ascertain the maximum temperature attainable in the drying chamber.

Results and Discussion

The thermal profile of the integrated hybrid solar dryer was obtained under no-load conditions through measurements of the drying chamber and the ambient air conditions as well as the temperature of the solar collector in a specified interval of time (Figure 2). The mean thermal output of the solar collector depends on the quantity of solar radiation incident on it which varies with the local daytime. High ambient relative humidity of the air in the early hours of the day results in low enthalpy of the drying air which necessitates the use of a supplemental heat unit – hybrid source. The drying chamber air temperature and solar air collector temperature increased with the local time with decreasing relative humidity, thus enhancing the vapour mixture of the drying fluid and its

moisture extraction capacity. These observations corroborate the findings of Nwakuba *et al.* (2020). As hourly time passes, the collector air temperature rises with a commensurate drop in relative humidity, indicating that local time and insolation flux are critical variables influencing collector thermal performance. Consequently, the relative humidity of the drying air in the drying chamber declines until the ambient temperature equilibrates with the drying chamber temperature. The heating by the solar collector increased the temperature in the drying chamber from 35.9°C to 58.1°C, even when the heating element was not activated. The highest recorded temperature of the solar collector was 57.5°C, while the average ambient temperature during the experiment was 39.3°C.

Figure 2 Variation of air conditions with local time.

The intensity of solar radiation influences both the thermal performance of the solar collector and the amount of heat that is contributed to the dryer system (Figure 3). The mean solar radiation intensity (I) ranges between $292.8 \leq I \leq 1305.2 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$. Within this range of solar intensity, the efficiency of the solar collector fluctuated between $40.1 \leq \eta_c \leq 88.3\%$ and, with a mean value of 47.5%. This suggests a greater prospect for an increased

moisture extraction rate from the solar air heater unit (solar collector) of a hybrid solar dryer system especially during elevated solar flux periods. The mean collector efficiency value changed proportionately with the amount of solar flux during the sunshine period as seen in Fig. 3. Previous studies by Bennamoun (2012), Fudholi *et al.* (2016), Hossain *et al.* (2018), and Nwakuba *et al.* (2020) produced similar findings.

Figure 3 Influence of solar intensity and hourly time on solar collector efficiency.

It has been observed that the heat generation capacity of the crop dryer using only the electric heat source under no-load testing is a function of running time, as depicted in Figure 4. As the running time extends, the resistance wire develops more thermal energy which heats the drying air by reducing its

absolute moisture, thereby boosting its moisture-carrying potential to effect drying. The relative humidity of the drying chamber was observed to maintain an opposite trend with the chamber temperature as a result of the relationship between drying air temperature and its moisture-holding capacity

arising from the higher energetic state of warm air which expands its volumetric capacity to accommodate more water vapour molecules. Moreover, the drying air at this time maintains a constant absolute humidity as its temperature increases per hourly time.

This implies that the same amount of water vapour diminishes to a smaller fraction of the air's total capacity, leading to a gross reduction in relative humidity, because of the drop in the ratio of actual moisture content to the air's capacity.

Figure 4 Thermal and relative humidity profiles of the drying chamber using the electric heat source.

After a running time of 140 minutes, the upper and lower trays in the drying chamber attained a maximum air temperature of 64.9 and 69.2°C, respectively which are suitable for drying fruity vegetables (Afolabi *et al.* 2014; Nwakuba *et al.*, 2020). The upper drying tray (rack) maintained a marginal continuous higher air temperature value than the lower drying rack with a 5% mean difference due to its proximity to the heat source. This, however, indicates a uniform

dissipation of convective heat flow through the rack layers for uniform drying with a negligible time lag between the two drying racks.

The efficiency of the thermal energy developed by the heating units of the dryer under no-load conditions was observed to be a function of time as shown in Figure 5. As the running time extends during a high sunshine period, more energy is generated efficiently to heat up the drying chamber to any desired

temperature level due to an increase in the solar collector heat input and constant resistance wire wattage. However, the energy

efficiency ranges between 50.5 and 75.5% which correspond to running times of 10:00 am and 1:30 pm, respectively.

Figure 5 Influence of drying running time on energy generation efficiency.

However, the mean energy efficiency of the system was obtained as 66.51% which is adequate for initiating internal water migration and surface evaporation of fresh fruits and vegetables (Afolabi *et al.*, 2014; Nwakuba *et al.*, 2017). The functional relationship of the energy efficiency (Eq. 15) is described by a polynomial expression with a correlation coefficient, R^2 of 0.9816. This statistical value closely correlates with energy variables like heater wattage, voltage, current, solar flux, and running time. This indicates that only running time can meaningfully correlate with the heat generation of the solar

air heater and resistance wire in a polynomial function:

$$\eta_e = -0.0004T^2 + 0.2276T + 42.973 \quad (15)$$

Where, η_e is the energy efficiency (%), and T is the running time (minutes).

For optimal and economical operation of the hybrid solar dryer, the drying air should be recycled through the heat recovery unit to enhance the system efficiency and minimize the energy consumption for drying.

Conclusion

The design and performance evaluation of a vegetable crop solar dryer integrated with heat

recovery units for the highly humid climate of Nigeria shows promising results. This system addresses the challenges of post-harvest losses and the need for sustainable drying technologies in tropical regions. A 5kg batch size hybrid solar dryer was designed and developed for drying fresh fruity vegetables. Various design factors ranging from material and machine factors to environmental factors were considered. No-load experimental validations were conducted to ascertain the efficiency of the dryer for handling moisture-laden crops like fruits and vegetables in humid climatic conditions. The drying chamber recorded a temperature range of 35.9 to 58.1°C through solar collector heating, which demonstrates high prospect of the solar component of the dryer system. The collector efficiency varied between 40.1 and 88.3% for a maximum and minimum solar radiation intensity of 1305.2 and 292.8 W/m², respectively. The electric resistance wire (heat source) generated a maximum air temperature of 69.2°C at 140 minutes of the running time. The heat generation efficiency of the system yields between 50.5 and 75.5% which was described by a polynomial regression function of R²-value of 0.9816. It is recommended that the dryer is run during low sunshine periods at varying air flow rates to determine the heat up times and heat generation efficiencies. Further

research and optimization can lead to broader implementation of similar systems, contributing to food security and reducing agricultural waste in Nigeria and other high-humidity regions.

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References

- Adedeji, A. A., Owamah, H. I., & Ogungbenle, H. N. (2018). Review of the drying process and systems analysis of solar drying in Nigeria. *Energy Reports*, 4, 618-638.
- Afolabi, T. J., Akintunde, T. Y., & Oyelade, O. J. (2014). Influence of drying conditions on the effective moisture diffusivity and energy requirements of ginger slices. *Journal of Food Research*, 3(2014), 103-112.
- Ajala, A. S., & Abubakar, M. A. (2018). Study of drying kinetics and quality attributes of fermented corn grains as affected by drying temperatures and velocities. *Journal of Nutrition Health and Food Engineering*, 8(2), 205-212. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jnhfe.2018.08.00270>

- Ambarita, H., Sembiring, P. G., Butarbutar, S., and Setiawan, E. Y. (2018). A preliminary test of a flat-plate solar collector of hybrid solar water heater. To cite this article: H Ambarita *et al.* *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1116, 032003.
- Bennamoun, L. (2012). An overview of the application of exergy and energy for determination of solar drying efficiency. *International Journal of Energy Engineering*, 2, 184-194. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijee.20120205.01>
- Bhardwaj, A., Tiwari, G. N., & Sodha, M. S. (2019). A comprehensive review of the application of solar dryers for agricultural and marine food products. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 111, 734-777.
- Bolaji, B. O. (2011). Exergetic analysis of solar energy drying systems. *Natural Resources*, 2, 92-97. <https://doi.org/10.4236/nr.2011.22012>
- Fang, G., Zhou, Y., Xu, W., & Zhao, Y. (2021). Recent advances in phase change materials for solar drying applications: A review. *Solar Energy*, 221, 676-691.
- Fudholi, A., Yendra, R., Basri, D. F., Ruslan, M. H., & Sopian, K. (2016). Energy and exergy analysis of hybrid solar drying system. *Contemporary Engineering Sciences*, 9, 215-223. <https://doi.org/10.12988/ces.2016.512323>
- Hossain, M. Z., Alam, M. M., Hossain, F., & Sarker, M. S. (2018). Performance evaluation of a cabinet solar dryer for drying red pepper in Bangladesh. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering*, 774, 100-109.
- Igbokwe, J. O., Ononogbo, C., & Okoronkwo, C. A. (2016). Control of thermal power plants' emissions: An imperative for the health of Nigerians and safe environment. *Journal of Global Ecology and Environment*, 4(4), 186-194.
- Jain, A., Tiwari, G. N., & Joshi, Y. (2020). A review of solar drying systems for agricultural produce. *Solar Energy*, 195, 56-73.
- Karlekar, B. V., & Desmond, R. M. (1982). *Engineering heat transfer*. West Publishing Company.
- Khaing, A. A., Oo, Z. M., Si, K. H., & Khaing, C. C. (2019). Solar collector design of dryer. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Technology Research*, 8, 280-283.
- Komolafe, C. A., & Waheed, M. A. (2018). Design and fabrication of a forced convection solar dryer integrated with heat storage materials. *Annales de Chimie - Science des Matériaux*, 1, 23-39. <https://doi.org/10.3166/ACSM.42.23-39>
- Kouadio, C. J., Ghislaine, D. N., Assoi, Y. D., Kouamé, L. P., & Kamenan, A. (2017). Biochemical and functional properties of yam flour during the post-harvest conservation of *Dioscorea Alata*. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 21(6), 1-10.
- Liley, P. E. (1997). Thermodynamic properties of substances. In Avallone,

- E. A., & Baumeister, T. (Eds.), *Mark's Standard Handbook for Mechanical Engineers*. McGraw Hill Books Co.
- Muhammad, J. Y., Abdullahi, A. Y., Abdulhamid, I. B., Abdulkadir, A. B., Ibrahim, I. U., Maikudi, M. M., and Aliyu, M. A. (2019). Design, construction, and performance assessment of a hybrid solar dryer using the forced convection principle. *International Journal of Energy and Smart Grid*, 4(1), 11-26. <https://doi.org/10.23884/IJESG>
- Nwakuba, N. R., Asoegwu, S. N., & Nwaigwe, K. N., & Chukwuezie, O. C. (2017). Design and development of a hybrid solar-electric dryer for sliced vegetable crops. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Technology*, 2, 48-64.
- Nwakuba, N. R., Ndukwu, M. C., Asonye, G. U., Asoegwu, S. N., & Nwandikom, G. I. (2020). Environmental sustainability analysis of a hybrid heat source dryer. *Polytechnica*, 3, 99-114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41050-020-00026-2>
- Okoronkwo, C. A., Okwu, M. O., Ononogbo, C., and Ezurike, B. O. (2018). The effect of different soil feedstock for the development of a soil-based microbial fuel cell. *American Journal of Earth Science and Engineering*, 1(2), 129-136.
- Ononogbo, C., Nwakuba, N. R., Nwaji, G. N., Nwifo, O. C., Nwosu, E. C., Okoronkwo, C. A., Igbokwe, J. O., & Anyanwu, E. E. (2022a). Investigation of the thermal profile of a crop dryer powered by generator exhaust gas waste heat. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Engineering*, 8(3), 2235-2241. <https://doi.org/10.29294/IJASE.8.3.2022.2235-2241>
- Ononogbo, C., Nwakuba, N. R., Nwaji, G. N., Nwifo, O. C., Nwosu, E. C., Okoronkwo, C. A., Igbokwe, J. O., & Anyanwu, E. E. (2022b). Thermal efficiency and drying behaviour of yam slices in a dryer driven by the waste heat of exhaust gases. *Scientific African*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e01310>
- Ononogbo, C., Nwifo, O. C., Nwakuba, N. R., Okoronkwo, C. A., Igbokwe, J. O., Nwadinobi, P. C., & Anyanwu, E. E. (2021). Energy parameters of corn drying in a hot air dryer powered by exhaust gas waste heat: An optimization case study of the food-energy nexus. *Energy Nexus*, 4, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nexus.2021.100029>
- Ononogbo, C., Nwifo, O. C., Okoronkwo, C. A., Ogueke, N. V., Igbokwe, J. O., & Anyanwu, E. E. (2020). Equipment sizing and method for the application of exhaust gas waste heat to food crops drying using a hot air tray dryer. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 13(5), 502-518. <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2020/v013i05/145593>
- Sevik, S. (2014). Design, experimental investigation, and analysis of a solar drying system. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 68, 227-234.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.01.013>

Sreekumar, A. (2007). Development of solar air heaters and thermal energy storage

system for drying applications in food processing industries (Doctoral dissertation, Cochin University of Science and Technology, Kochi-22, India).